

Security: A Cloud way

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Abstract

Security in today's scenario is very difficult task to achieve. Since, everyday a new threat comes to affect the information causing a huge loss of data, loss of time to get rid of that threat, in turn resulting in financial loss. There are tools which are widely used to defend against these malicious files, such as, antivirus software, intrusion detection and prevention software, firewalls, spyware. But long term use of these tools is questionable. This paper describes a new way of looking at these security tools. This will argue on a new trend for security as a cloud network services.

Keywords – Threat, Malicious files, Spyware, Antivirus software, Intrusion Detection and Prevention software.

1. INTRODUCTION

Information security is difficult task to achieve in today's scenario where each day a new threat comes to be the next best infection to sliced bread. It is quite difficult to measure data security on the basis of confidentiality, integrity, and availability in today's world of information system. Today the security services are basically hardware based physical devices that are install on the system and that work to prevent hostile intrusion into the system.

Antivirus softwares are one of the most widely used tools for detection and deletion of malicious and unwanted files. Other tools such as intrusion detection and prevention softwares, firewalls, spywares, etc. are used in industries to prevent information theft. All these tools are host based that means these work on individual machine to protect it. However, a long term use of these tools is questionable. There is a significant vulnerability window between when a threat first appears and when vendors generate a signature. Moreover, a substantial percentage of malware is never detected by these tools. This means that end systems with the latest security tool and signatures can still be vulnerable for long periods of time.

The second important trend is that the increasing complexity of security tools and services has indirectly resulted in vulnerabilities that can and are being exploited by malware.

In this paper we suggest a new way of looking at these security issues and security tools.

- **Security in the Cloud:** Security services are embedded within the service provider's network. And internet born threats are detected and blocked before they reach to individual system.

This new way in the world of information security provides several benefits given in [1], such as, better detection of malicious software, enhanced forensics capabilities, retrospective detection, and improved deployability and management.

This paper describes how internet based cloud services can provide full security solutions. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background on the Security. Section 3 gives the Limitations of the Security tools used up till now. Section 4 describes the Security in the cloud. Section 5 presents few advantages as well as disadvantages of using cloud services. Section 6 gives an overview of one Case study on security in cloud computing. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the paper.

2. SECURITY BACKGROUND

Security is the degree of protection against danger, corruption and actions resulting in the loss of data. The term refers to the security to the system as well as information from unauthorized access, use, disclosure, disruption, modification or destruction. There are so many tools and protection technologies used now a days for providing security to the information against web threats.

Every day a new threat comes at the corner of the internet becoming the next best ever infection to our data. It has become a difficult task to measure data security on the basis of conventional parameters, such as, confidentiality, integrity, and availability. Security services today are basically hardware based physical devices that are install on the end system, and are controlled by the user who don't even know the origin of the threat affecting the whole information system.

Network security services are typically customer premises based equipment which rely on the security features built into the devices. The most common security services include firewall, intrusion detection and prevention and anti-malware. As hardware is inherently 'fixed', it must be manually updated with the latest information on viruses, malware and signatures in order to function effectively. Keeping up to date with this information is difficult task.

For this reason, it is usually more powerful – and cost-effective – to supplement control with network-based security. Also networked based system allows to save the space required for the system.

Here we are going to discuss the limitations of traditional security tools, which are host based and how to overcome all those using a cloud computing as one of the most powerful tool for information security.

3. LIMITATIONS of the SECURITY TOOLS

Antivirus software is one of the most successful and widely used tools for detecting and stopping malicious and unwanted software. Antivirus software is deployed on most desktops and workstations in enterprises across the world. Also other security tools used are firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention softwares, anti-malware, etc. which are used world wide for the security reasons. All these tools need regular updates so as to combat against the new security threats. Then also more of these tools fail to detect a significant percentage of malware in the wild.

Moreover, there is a significant vulnerability window between when a threat first appears and when antivirus vendors generate a signature or modify their software to detect the threat. This means that end systems with the latest antivirus software and signatures can still be vulnerable for long periods of time. Also complexity of antivirus software and services has indirectly resulted in vulnerabilities that can and are being exploited by malware. That is, malware is actually using vulnerabilities in antivirus software as means to infect systems.

Recovering from infections also presents new challenges. In some cases, Web threats may result in a system infection that is so extensive (for example, via a rootkit in which the system file is replaced) that conventional uninstall or system cleaning approaches become useless. Infected systems often require a complete system recovery, in which the hard drive is wiped and the operating system, applications, and user data are reinstalled.

As a result, information security today is at a critical turning point: a new approach is needed to address the newest class of threats.

4. SECURITY in CLOUD

Clearly, security needs a new approach to addressing Web threats that complements existing techniques. This new approach must incorporate a range of protective measures. Any effective approach should also address all relevant protocols, because Web threats leverage multiple protocols

in their attacks, in particular email as the initial delivery mechanism and the Web as the threat host. However, other mechanisms can also help perpetrate attacks such as links in IM and infected files. Coordinating measures requires efficient, centralized management of region-specific expertise to help address the regional and even localized nature of many of the threats [3].

We argue that the security service currently provided by host-based antivirus software can be efficiently and effectively provided as an in-cloud network service. Instead of running complex analysis software on every end host, we suggest that each end host run a lightweight process to acquire executables entering a system, send them to a network service for analysis, and then run or quarantine them based on a threat report returned by the network service [2].

Internet-based “in-the-cloud” services can provide full security solutions or deploy specific technologies that supplement on-site products. These in-the-cloud services reduce the load on the network and enable the rapid exchange of information necessary to respond to threats as they appear. It also provides Protocol protection, security technologies having components, such as, Web Reputation, Roaming Protection, Global Collaboration, Proactive protection, and a real time service feedback and integration [3].

4.1 SECURITY

Security in the cloud refers to managed security services which are embedded within a service provider network and detect and block Internet-borne threats before they even reach an organization’s perimeter defenses, let alone the endpoint. Security in the cloud redirects traffic through a central security platform, thus identifying and stopping bad traffic before it reaches the client. It provides a fully designed and deployed range of security services that can be subscribed to on demand. The centralized nature of the solution means clients can make savings both in terms of efficiency of response to threats and in investment in hardware and IT expertise internally [4].

Therefore, security in the cloud can also help make large energy savings, and allow the removal of hardware from within organizations, thus freeing up network capacity and accommodation.

Right now, most users purchase a wide range of security devices, from antivirus software to firewalls to intrusion detection and prevention systems. With an in-the-cloud setup, however, many of these tasks can be handled using a virtual device administered by a managed security service provider (MSSP). Essentially, this works as a software-as-a-service model, replacing product, installation and maintenance costs [4].

5. ADVANTAGES and DISADVANTAGES

As every coin has two sides, head and tail, using cloud computing as a security tool to our data has advantages as well as few disadvantages.

5.1 ADVANTAGES

- **Reduced Cost:** It can prove cost-effective in the long run as well as significantly reducing organization's carbon footprint.
- **Increased Storage:** Organizations can store more data than on private computer systems.
- **Highly Automated:** IT personnel not needed to keep software up to date as maintenance is the job of the service provider on the cloud.
- **Allows to Shift Focus:** No longer having to worry about constant security updates.[5]

5.2 DISADVANTAGES

- **Data Traffic:** Security in the cloud necessitates a form of monitoring and filtering of data traffic.
- **Freedom:** For some, this represents a threat to the essence of the Internet itself.

6. CASE STUDY

In order to move the detection of malicious and unwanted files from end hosts and into the network, several important challenges must be overcome: (1) unlike existing antivirus software, files must be transported into the network for analysis; (2) an efficient analysis system must be constructed to handle the analysis of files from many different hosts using many different detection engines in parallel; and (3) the performance of the system must be similar or better than existing detection systems such as antivirus software.

To address these problems we have studied one case study of antivirus architecture which is proposed in [1]. This architecture includes three major components. The first is a lightweight host agent run on end systems like desktops, laptops, and mobile devices that identifies new files and sends them into the network for analysis. The second is a network service that receives files from the host agent, identifies malicious and unwanted content, and instructs hosts whether access to the files is safe. The third

component is an archival and forensics service that stores information about what files were analyzed and provides a query and alerting interface for operators. Fig. 1 shows the high level architecture approach.

6.1 CLIENT SOFTWARE

Malicious and unwanted files can enter an organization from many sources. For example, mobile devices, USB drives, email attachments, downloads, and vulnerable network services are all common entry points. Due to the broad range of entry vectors, the proposed architecture uses a lightweight file acquisition agent run on each end system.

The host agent runs on each end host and inspects each file on the system. Access to each file is trapped and diverted to a handling routine which begins by generating a unique identifier (UID) of the file and comparing that identifier against a cache of previously analyzed files. If a file UID is not present in the cache then the file is sent to the in-cloud network service for analysis. To make the analysis process more efficient, the architecture provides a method for sending a file for analysis as soon as it is written on the end host's file system (e.g., via file-copy, installation, or download). Doing so amortizes the transmission and analysis cost over the time elapsed between file creation and system or user-initiated access.

6.2 NETWORK SERVICE

The second major component of the architecture is the network service responsible for file analysis. The core task of the network service is to determine whether a file is malicious or unwanted. Unlike existing systems, each file is analyzed by a collection of detection engines. That is, each file is analyzed by multiple detection engines in parallel and a final determination of whether a file is malicious or unwanted is made by aggregating these individual results to a threat report.

6.3 ARCHIVAL and FORENSIC SERVICES

The third and final component of the architecture is a service that provides information on file usage across participating hosts which can assist in post-infection forensic analysis. It has been opted for a lightweight solution consisting of file access information sent by the host agent and stored securely by the network service, in addition to the behavioral profiles of malicious software generated by the behavioral detection engines. Depending on the privacy policy of organization, a tunable amount of

Fig. 1 Architectural approach for in-cloud files analysis services

forensics information can be logged and sent to the archival service. For example, a more security conscious organization could specify that information about every executable launch be recorded and sent to the archival service.

7. CONCLUSION

Web threats are prevalent today and are growing in numbers and impact. Because conventional approaches fail to protect against Web threats, the information security industry is at a crossroads. To address the ever-growing sophistication and threat of modern malicious software, cloud computing is the right solution to secure the data. This will provide a new paradigm to looking to all information security issues and that by the "Cloud Way".

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